

**Jean-Paul Faguet,
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Publicly funded research should be publicly available

– Jean Paul Faguet

Academic research is publicly funded so should be freely available to the public. It is particularly important that research is available to people and institutions that would benefit from it.

An increasing number of academics are advocating for open access publishing. They think people across the world – fellow academics, but also society in general – should have equal access to research and knowledge.

Jean-Paul Faguet, Professor of the Political Economy of Development at London School of Economics and Political Science and a Fellow of the Academy of Social Sciences, feels very strongly about this, not least because his work involves countries where access to research is currently very limited.

Where access is denied

Faguet says his many of his peers in institutions in countries such as Africa and Latin America are denied access to research, particularly research coming out of the most prestigious and influential publishers. He says research and knowledge should be freely available to everybody who wants and needs it, particularly if the research is about them and their country.

He recently co-authored an open access monograph called *Decentralised Governance: Crafting Effective Democracies Around the World*. Published by LSE

Press, it involved 23 academics. They chose LSE Press because it offered open access. Faguet said:

“ Open access is, for all of us, a really big deal. The people we study live in developing countries, and the results, conclusions and recommendations – the main point of this research – is really aimed at developing countries, first and foremost. We can’t go and get data and experience from developing countries and then lock it up behind a paywall where they can’t see it.

Paying twice for research

There is another reason why Faguet advocates for open access. Academics are paid to conduct research so he thinks it is wrong that anyone – person or institution - should have to pay again to access that research.

He explains:

“I just don’t think it’s right that the public has to pay twice. By funding our research grants and paying our salaries, they already paid to produce the research. Why should anyone have to pay again, just because it has been put behind a paywall?”

Faguet said he and his co-authors are all committed to the same principles – making the research freely available, rather than it going to a select few and publishers making money from it. The publisher waived costs that could not be covered by grants or other open access funding.

Open access benefits research

By publishing open access, Faguet says research reaches a far bigger, wider audience. This means it has more impact. Firstly, because people can access it and secondly because they can then act on it. He said:

“ A book published with a normal press is going to make it into a fraction of the world’s university libraries. We got our first citation within a day of publication, which never happens.

Faguet says there was also more flexibility about what was included in the monograph and how content could be presented. He and his fellow authors were able to include many more charts, graphs and illustrations than is customary in traditional publishing. This is a very useful, important consideration when producing a monograph about economics, where charts and graphs are a key way of demonstrating findings.